

Optimization for Communication and Networks

Class Project

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Maximum Lifetime Routing

1. Task 1: Python program and result for node 1 as a central node

```
#Python_code_for_Maximum_lifetime_routing
#Python program for maximum lifetime routing in WSNs
#November 2017
from pulp import*
#default case: central node 0 located at sensor node 1
#Change a node to 0 if it is to be as a central node,
#for example if the central node is to be 4 then change
#p to P = {1:(20,60),2:(40,40),3:(40,100),0:(60,20),5:(60,80),
#6:(80,40),7:(80,100),8:(100,80)}
#####

P = {0:(20,60),2:(40,40),3:(40,100),4:(60,20),5:(60,80),6:(80,40),\
     7:(80,100),8:(100,80)} #node positions (m)
R = 60 #coverage radius (m)
N = P.keys() #set of all nodes (node 0 being central node)
Np = [i for i in P.keys() if i!= 0] #N'= set of sensor nodes
#with traffic
D = {} #dictionary whose keys are links and whose values are
#distances (m)
A = {} #dictionary whose keys are nodes and whose values are
#adjacent nodes
for i in N:
    A[i] = []
    for j in [j for j in N if j!=i]:
        tmp = pow(P[i][0]-P[j][0],2)+pow(P[i][1]-P[j][1],2)
        if tmp<=pow(R,2):
            D[(i,j)] = tmp
            A[i].append(j)
L = D.keys(); #set of links
t = dict([(i,0.1) for i in Np]) #traffic from sensor
#nodes (packet/s)
PE_elec = 50e-6 #energy for transmitting/receiving
#1 bit (J/bit)
PE_amp = 100e-9 #energy dissipation from transmit
#amplifier (J/bit/m^2)
gamma = 2 #path loss exponent
alpha_t = {}
for l in L:
```

```

    alpha_t[1] = PE_elec + PE_amp\*timesD[1]
    alpha_r = PE_elec
    E = 1000.0 #initial battery energy (J)

#####
prob = LpProblem('MLR_WSN',LpMinimize)
f = LpVariable.dicts('f',(Np,L),0,None,LpContinuous)
Linv = LpVariable('Linv',0,None,LpContinuous)

#objective
prob += Linv
#prob += Linv >= 0

#####
#constraint: definition of Linv
for i in Np:
    prob+=E*Linv>=lpSum(alpha_t[1]\*timesf[k][1] for k in Np for
        l in L if l[0]==i)+lpSum(alpha_r\*timesf[k][1] for k in Np
            for l in L if l[1]==i)#Sinc the alpha_r is always
            #constant for each link which satisfies the conditiion
            #of range, so we can use it as a constanat

#constraint: flow conservation

for i in N :
    for k in Np:
        if i==k:
            prob+=lpSum(f[k][1] for l in L if l[1]==i)-lpSum(f[k][1]
                for l in L if l[0]==i)==-t[k]
        elif i==0:
            prob+=lpSum(f[k][1] for l in L if l[1]==i)-lpSum(f[k][1]
                for l in L if l[0]==i)==t[k]
        else:
            prob+=lpSum(f[k][1] for l in L if l[1]==i)-lpSum(f[k][1]
                for l in L if l[0]==i)==0
    for k in Np:
        for l in L:
            prob+=f[k][1]>=0

#####

prob.writeLP('MLR_WSN.lp')
prob.solve(GLPK())
print 'Status:', LpStatus[prob.status]
print 'Optimal cost:', value(prob.objective)
for i in prob.variables(): #print only nonzero variables
    if value(i)!=0:
        print i,value(i)

#nework lifetime (day)
print 'Lifetime:', 1/value(prob.objective)/3600.0/24.0

```

Result:

```
GLPSOL: GLPK LP/MIP Solver, v4.61
Parameter(s) specified in the command line:
—cpxlp /tmp/22644-pulp.lp -o /tmp/22644-pulp.sol
Reading problem data from '/tmp/22644-pulp.lp'...
315 rows, 253 columns, 1211 non-zeros
514 lines were read
GLPK Simplex Optimizer, v4.61
315 rows, 253 columns, 1211 non-zeros
Preprocessing...
63 rows, 253 columns, 959 non-zeros
Scaling...
A: min|aij| = 5.000e-05 max|aij| = 1.000e+03 ratio = 2.000e+07
GM: min|aij| = 3.492e-01 max|aij| = 2.864e+00 ratio = 8.200e+00
EQ: min|aij| = 1.220e-01 max|aij| = 1.000e+00 ratio = 8.200e+00
Constructing initial basis...
Size of triangular part is 56
      0: obj = 0.000000000e+00 inf = 4.901e-03 (10)
     18: obj = 5.290361446e-08 inf = 2.180e-19 (0)
    * 34: obj = 4.293478261e-08 inf = 5.720e-19 (0)
OPTIMAL LP SOLUTION FOUND
Time used: 0.0 secs
Memory used: 0.4 Mb (393824 bytes)
Writing basic solution to '/tmp/22644-pulp.sol'...
Status: Optimal
Optimal cost: 4.29348e-08
Linv 4.29348e-08
f_2_(2,_0) 0.1
f_3_(3,_0) 0.1
f_4_(4,_0) 0.1
f_5_(5,_0) 0.1
f_6_(2,_0) 0.1
f_6_(6,_2) 0.1
f_7_(3,_0) 0.0597826
f_7_(4,_0) 0.0141304
f_7_(5,_0) 0.026087
f_7_(6,_4) 0.0141304
f_7_(6,_5) 0.00717391
f_7_(7,_3) 0.0597826
f_7_(7,_5) 0.018913
f_7_(7,_8) 0.0213043
f_7_(8,_6) 0.0213043
f_8_(2,_0) 0.0663043
f_8_(5,_0) 0.0336957
f_8_(6,_2) 0.0663043
f_8_(8,_5) 0.0336957
f_8_(8,_6) 0.0663043
Lifetime: 269.573261645
```

From the result it is clear that the problem is “optimal” when node 1 being as central node with “optimal cost = 4.29348×10^{-8} ” and with “life time = 269.573261645 (sec)”.

2. Task2 :Drawing of routing taken form each of sensor node to central node [node 1]

$$f_{20}^2 = 0.1, f_{30}^3 = 0.1, f_{40}^4 = 0.1, f_{50}^5 = 0.1, f_{20}^6 = 0.1, f_{62}^6 = 0.1, f_{30}^7 = 0.0597826, f_{40}^7 = 0.0141304, f_{50}^7 = 0.026087, f_{64}^7 = 0.0141304, f_{65}^7 = 0.00717391, f_{73}^7 = 0.0597826, f_{75}^7 = 0.018913, f_{78}^7 = 0.0213043, f_{86}^7 = 0.0213043, f_{20}^8 = 0.0663043, f_{50}^8 = 0.0336957, f_{62}^8 = 0.0663043, f_{85}^8 = 0.0336957, f_{86}^8 = 0.0663043,$$

Lifetime : 269.573261645

3. **Task3 : Indicating lifetimes and optimal cost** [with node “ p_i ” as central node]

Node p_i	Life Time(sec)	Optimal Cost(packet/sec)
1	269.573261454	4.29343×10^{-8}
2	300.467652662	3.85202×10^{-8}
3	275.891123912	4.19516×10^{-8}
4	271.829708821	4.25784×10^{-8}
5	386.59751474	2.99383×10^{-8}
6	328.044727455	3.5282×10^{-8}
7	274.826580031	4.21141×10^{-8}
8	231.637141641	4.99664×10^{-8}

Table 1: Table indicating parameters when different nodes acts as central node

Conclusion: It is clear from Table 1 that Lifetime and optimal cost follows the central node order (greatest lifetime to least lifetime with optimization in cost).

Order[1:8] = Node(p_5), Node(p_6), Node(p_2), Node(p_3), Node(p_7), Node(p_4), Node(p_1), Node(p_8).

p_5 , i.e Node 5 is having Maximum Lifetime of routing with most optimal cost. The Maximum Lifetime routing for the given network with p_5 as a central node is 386.59751474(sec) and with optimal cost 2.99383×10^{-8} (packets/sec).